

Heparin-affinity chromatography is a generic purification platform for chimeric gag VLPs displaying different viral surface antigens

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ABSTRACT

Chimeric virus-like particles formed by the co-expression of HIV-1 gag capsid protein and surface proteins from other viruses can be used as a platform for production of a wide range of viral vaccines. These virus-like particles can be rapidly produced in an insect cell culture using the baculovirus expression vector system. However, a variety of different process-related impurities such as host cell proteins, double stranded DNA, chromatin, and structurally similar bionanoparticles like extracellular vesicles and baculovirus particles are present in the harvested supernatant and complicate the chromatographic purification steps. Heparan sulfate is the first entry point of a lot of enveloped viruses into the cell. Taking advantage of this functional property, its sub-variant, the glycosaminoglycan heparin immobilized on a chromatography media is a universal tool for the separation of enveloped virus-like particles. A purification process was developed consisting of clarification of the cell culture supernatant by membrane filtration, a pre-purification step using core-shell bead flow-through chromatography with Capto™ Core 700, followed by heparin affinity chromatography with Capto™ Heparin. The combination of Capto™ Core 700 and Capto™ Heparin allows for direct load of the flow-through material from the first into the second step without buffer exchange in between. In addition, lengthy buffer screening, as required for ion exchange and multimodal chromatography, can be omitted. Linear salt gradient elution in heparin affinity chromatography enabled separation of virus-like particles and baculovirus. The platformability of the process was demonstrated by purification of virus-like particles expressing influenza A virus hemagglutinin or neuraminidase, or SARS-CoV-2 spike protein as surface antigens and the virus-like particle without co-expressed surface protein. Western blotting, host cell protein and DNA assays, TCID50 (for residual baculovirus), mass spectrometry, multi-angle light scattering and nanoparticle tracking analysis were used to characterize the different fractions obtained during the purification. A similar elution profile was obtained for all tested virus-like particles and deviations could be explained by batch-to-batch variations and differences in productivity for the different constructs. Double stranded DNA was reduced to 7 – 36 ng/10⁹ particles and host cell protein content was below the limit of quantification; in the main product fraction an average seven-fold reduction of baculovirus and a yield of 9 % – 14 % of bound particles with a concentration of 1.4 – 1.8 × 10¹⁰ particles/mL in the eluate were achieved meeting requirements for a viral vaccine. Accordingly, this process is suitable as a downstream process platform for chimeric HIV-1 gag-based VLP products.

1. Introduction

Chimeric enveloped virus-like particles (VLPs), formed by the co-

expression of a structural protein from a virus such as the HIV-1 gag capsid protein along with different surface proteins from other viruses, can be used as an efficient platform for the production of a wide range of

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viral vaccines [1,2]. Their production via the baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS) in insect cells is a well-established process [2–6]. By co-expression of a viral matrix protein, such as the HIV-1 gag, and a surface antigen of any virus, a VLP is budded from the insect cell displaying the selected viral protein at the surface. Advantages of the BEVS are the robust expression and, due to the large genome size of the baculovirus, the possibility of co-expression of large surface antigens along with the structural proteins essential for VLP formation [2,3,6–9]. Besides the common process- and product-related impurities like host cell DNA, chromatin, proteins and extracellular vesicles (EVs), the expression of VLPs in the insect cell system using BEVS generates also the recombinant baculovirus itself, which is a critical impurity due to its structural similarities to the VLPs [10–18]. Baculovirus particles display similar proteins on the surface as VLPs, because they are budded from the same cell membrane, with minor differences in their shape and size. This presents unique challenges in both downstream processing and analytical methods to separate and analyze them, respectively. However, baculovirus can be detected by cytopathic assays such as TCID₅₀ whereas VLPs cannot. Although different purification techniques such as filtration, ultracentrifugation or precipitation have been tried [5,18–21], chromatography-based methods are still seen as the most effective approach for VLP purification in regard to both purity and scalability [5,6,10,12,22].

In the recent development of downstream processing for VLPs, a two-step chromatography process for purification and separation has proven successful in obtaining high-purity VLPs consisting of a flow-through chromatography using core-shell beads (Capto™ Core 700) followed by heparin affinity chromatography (Capto™ Heparin) [12,14]. The core-shells are composed of an inert outer layer with a cut-off of 700 kDa and a core with octylamine ligands [23,24]. Large particles like VLPs, baculovirus or EVs are excluded and can be collected in the flow-through fraction. Proteins, DNA fragments and other impurities can enter the pores and are bound by the multimodal ligand [12]. The second chromatographic step is based on heparin affinity [12,14,22]. Heparin is a more sulfated, tissue-specific variant of the polysaccharide Heparan sulfate [22,25]. Heparan sulfate can be found in all multicellular animals as ubiquitous component of the cell surface and extracellular matrix and it has been identified as possible point of entry for viruses [14,26–29]. Heparan sulfate and its sub-variant heparin have the ability to bind viruses, which makes them interesting ligands for affinity chromatography for virus purification. The Capto™ Heparin resin has been used to separate virus-like particles and extracellular vesicles produced in HEK 293 and CHO cells by linear gradient elution [12,14].

Although the described two-step chromatographic method has been shown to be effective for the purification of naked enveloped VLPs produced in mammalian cells (HEK 293 and CHO) [12,14], its application as a possible platform process for chimeric VLPs produced in insect cells using BEVS has not yet been demonstrated. The possibility of the BEVS for co-expression of viral structural proteins and surface antigens enables a wide variety of possible chimeric VLPs. For instance, the HIV-1 gag protein, which triggers the VLP budding process [12], has been co-expressed with various surface proteins such as hemagglutinin (HA) from influenza virus, HER2 protein or the spike protein from SARS-CoV-2 in order to alter the biological response of the VLP [7,8,30]. The ideal downstream processing for such a chimeric VLP production platform should be effective independently from the presence of different antigens on the VLP surface. In this work we investigated the applicability of flow-through chromatography followed by heparin affinity chromatography as a purification platform for chimeric VLPs produced in insect cells using BEVS with different surface antigens. For that purpose, four VLP constructs based on the HIV-1 gag VLP were tested: HIV-1 gag without surface antigen (“gag-naked”), HIV-1 gag with Hemagglutinin-1 from Influenza A virus (“gag-HA”), HIV-1 gag with Neuraminidase-2 from Influenza A virus (“gag-NA”) and HIV-1 gag with spike protein (S1) from SARS-CoV-2 (“gag-S”). Removal of critical impurities such as host cell proteins, DNA and chromatin was evaluated.

Moreover, the separation of different particle populations was investigated.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Chemicals and standards

All chemicals were acquired from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) or Abcam (Cambridge, England) and were of analytical grade, if not otherwise stated.

2.2. Biological constructs (VLP types) and cell line

For VLP production, the Tnms42 insect cell line (free of latent nodavirus infection and negatively tested for mycoplasma) was used. All four VLP constructs produced had the HIV-1 gag polyprotein as capsid protein. Three of the four produced VLPs additionally carried a co-expressed surface protein: “gag-HA” - Hemagglutinin (HA) from A/Puerto Rico/8/1934(H1N1); “gag-NA” - Neuraminidase 2 (NA) from Influenza A Kansas/14/2017(H3N2), segment 6 neuraminidase (NA) gene; and “gag-S” - S protein (spike) from the SARS-CoV-2 Wuhan-1 reference strain.

2.3. Expression of HIV-1 gag VLPs in baculovirus-insect cell system

Tnms42 cells were cultivated at a cell density of 2×10^6 cells/mL in 1800 mL Fernbach shaking flasks (VWR International, Radnor, PA, USA) at 27 °C and 110 rpm. A working volume of 330 mL was used. Cell cultures were infected with the respective baculovirus stock carrying the genetic information for the HIV-1 gag protein and the co-expressed surface antigen at an MOI of 3. Cells were harvested 3 days post-infection.

2.4. Cell culture clarification

The cell culture supernatants were centrifuged (5 min at 500 G followed by 10 min at 1000 G) and filtrated with a 0.8 µm Cellulose Nitrate Nalgene™ Rapid-Flow™ Sterile Disposable Filter Unit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) in order to remove cell debris and other large impurities.

2.5. Chromatographic experiments

2.5.1. Chromatographic system

All chromatographic experiments were performed with an ÄKTA Pure 150 M2 instrument equipped with a sample pump S9 and a fraction collector F9-C (GE Healthcare, Uppsala, Sweden). Unicorn software 6.4.1 was used for data collection. The following parameters were monitored: UV signals at 280 and 260 nm as well as conductivity. For online monitoring of particle concentration by multiangle light scattering (MALS), the chromatographic system was coupled to a DAWN 8 MALS detector (Wyatt Technology, Santa Barbara, California) via a versatile valve. The detector’s mV signal at 10 % laser power, detector 5 (90° angle) and an output slope of 0.2 was directly displayed and recorded in the Unicorn software.

2.5.2. Chromatography media and column hardware

For the pre-purification using core-shell beads, columns were packed with Capto™ Core 700 resin (Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden). For the heparin affinity chromatography, Capto™ Heparin (Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden) was used. All columns were packed in HiScale 16/20 column housings (Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden).

2.5.3. Mobile phases

All chromatographic experiments were performed using 50 mM HEPES, pH 7.2 as mobile phase A and 50 mM HEPES, 2 M NaCl, pH 7.2

Table 1

Column volumes, flow rates for a residence time of 5 min and loading volumes for the chromatographic columns used in the VLP purification processes (equivalent to 20 CV and 10 CV for Capto™ Core 700 and Capto™ Heparin, respectively).

Surface antigen	naked	HA	NA	S
Capto™ Core 700				
CV [mL]	9.25	10.86	11.86	10.05
Flow rate [mL/min]	1.85	2.18	2.38	2.00
Loading volume [mL]	184.98	217.20	237.26	201.06
Capto™ Heparin				
CV [mL]	9.05	10.86	12.47	10.66
Flow rate [mL/min]	1.81	2.17	2.50	2.13
Loading volume [mL]	90.48	108.60	124.66	106.56

as mobile phase B. Different concentrations of the modifier (NaCl) for linear gradient elution were obtained by mixing mobile phases A and B using the chromatography system. For the cleaning-in-place (CIP) steps, 1 M NaOH with 30 % 2-Propanol (Capto™ Core 700) and 0.1 M NaOH (Capto™ Heparin) were used.

2.5.4. Capto™ Core pre-purification

Before loading, columns were charged at 100 % mobile phase B (equivalent to 2 M NaCl) and equilibrated with 5 % mobile phase B (equivalent to 100 mM NaCl). For each run, 20 column volumes (CV) of clarified VLP material were loaded onto the respective column, followed by a 4 CV wash step (at 100 mM NaCl) and a 2 CV linear salt gradient for elution (from 100 mM to 2 M NaCl followed by a 4 CV hold step at 2 M NaCl). For column maintenance, CIP using 1 M NaOH and 30 % 2-Propanol was performed. The following fractions were collected for the Capto™ Core runs: load (LCC), flow-through (FTCC), wash (WCC), elution (ELCC); The residence time throughout the whole process was 5 min. Detailed information regarding the column volumes (CV), flow rates and loading volumes for each VLP construct can be found in [Table 1](#).

2.5.5. Capto™ heparin purification

Before loading, columns were charged at 100 % mobile phase B (equivalent to 2 M NaCl) and equilibrated in 5 % mobile phase B (equivalent to 100 mM NaCl). For every run, 10 CV pre-purified material (FTCC) were loaded onto the column, followed by a 3 CV wash step at 100 mM NaCl. Elution was performed by a linear salt gradient, starting at 100 mM NaCl until 1268 mM NaCl over 20 CV, followed by a 4 CV hold step at 2000 mM NaCl for column regeneration. For column maintenance, a CIP step (0.1 M NaOH) was applied. Samples were collected throughout the runs as follows: the flow-through during the load phase was split into three equal fractions (3.33 CV) and the wash was collected as a whole. For the elution, the first 12 CV, where the peaks were expected, were collected in fractions of 2 CV (resulting in the elution fractions EL1 – EL6). The remaining 8 CV in the elution were collected as a whole (EL7), as well as the regeneration (Reg). The residence time throughout the whole process was 5 min. Detailed information regarding the column volumes (CV), flow rates and loading volumes for each VLP construct can be found in [Table 1](#).

For the heparin affinity chromatography, the recovery of bound particles ($R_{\text{bound particles}}$) was calculated by dividing the total particle number of a specific fraction ($TPN_{\text{elution fraction}}$, i.e. the respective recovered particles) by the total number of bound particles, which is the total particle number of the load (TPN_{Load}) minus all unbound fractions, i.e. flow-through fractions and wash fraction ($TPN_{\text{unbound particles}}$):

$$R_{\text{bound particles}} = \frac{TPN_{\text{elution fraction}}}{TPN_{\text{Load}} - TPN_{\text{unbound particles}}}$$

2.6. Determination of total protein and double stranded DNA content

For determination of total protein content, Bradford assay with Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) for protein staining was used. The assay was performed in a 96-well plate according to the manufacturer's instructions. The calibration curve was obtained by diluting bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard with TE-buffer to a concentration range from 12.5 to 200 µg/mL.

Double stranded DNA (dsDNA) was determined by Quant-iT Pico-Green dsDNA kit (Life Technologies, Waltham, MA, USA) in a 96-well plate according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Signals for protein and dsDNA content were measured with a GenusPro Plate Reader (Tecan, Männedorf, Switzerland).

2.7. Sodium dodecyl sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and Western blotting

SDS-PAGES were performed in an X-cell SureLock Mini-Cell electrophoresis chamber (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA), using NuPAGE Bis/Tris 4–12 % gels (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) and reduced MES-SDS running conditions at 200 V and 400 mA for 50 min. Samples were prepared with NuPAGE LDS sample buffer (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) and reduced at 99 °C for 15 min in the presence of 182 mM dithiothreitol (DTT). For each sample, a volume of 20 µL (12-well gels), 15 µL (15-well gels) or 12 µL (17-well gels) was loaded in a gel lane. Precision Plus Protein Unstained marker (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) was used as molecular weight marker for SDS-PAGES. For Western blots, SeeBlue Plus2 Pre-stained Protein Standard (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) was used. Protein bands in the gels for the SDS-PAGES were stained with Flamingo Fluorescent Protein Gel Stain (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA).

For Western blot analysis after SDS-PAGE, proteins were transferred from the gel to a 0.2 mm nitrocellulose membrane using the Trans-Blot Turbo™ Transfer System (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Membranes were blocked overnight with 3 % w/v BSA in PBS-T (0.1 % w/v Tween-20 in PBS). Detection was performed using a two-step procedure: First, the membranes were incubated with the following primary antibodies diluted 1:1000 in PBS-T containing 1 % w/v BSA for 2 h: mouse monoclonal antibody against HIV-1 p24 (abcam, Cambridge, United Kingdom), rabbit monoclonal antibody against baculovirus vp39 (ProteoGenix, Schiltigheim, France), rabbit monoclonal antibody against Histone H3 (abcam, Cambridge, United Kingdom), rabbit monoclonal antibody against Influenza A virus H1N1 HA (Hemagglutinin) (GeneTex, Irvine, CA, USA), rabbit polyclonal antibody against Influenza A virus Neuraminidase 2 (Invitrogen, Waltham, MA, USA), rabbit polyclonal antibody against SARS-CoV-2 S1 (Cosagen, Tartumaa, Estonia). The second step was the incubation of the membranes with the respective anti-mouse or anti-rabbit IgG conjugated with alkaline phosphatase (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), diluted 1:1000 in PBS-T with 1 % w/v BSA for 1 h. Premixed BCIP/NBT solution (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) was used as substrate for visualizing the alkaline phosphatase conjugates.

2.8. Particle concentration and size distribution determination

For determination of the particle concentration and particle size distribution, nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) was used. Experiments were performed on a NanoSight NS300 (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Worcestershire, UK) with a 488 nm laser module. Samples were diluted in distilled, particle-free water to a final concentration of 20 – 100 particles per frame. Three different dilutions were measured per sample. Five videos of 30 s were captured for each dilution at a temperature of 25 °C. The camera level was set to 14 and the detection threshold to 5.

Table 2

Comparison of the particle recovery and cell viability at harvest of the different gag VLP production runs.

Surface antigen	particle concentration (part/mL)				recovery (%)				cell viability (%)			
	naked	HA	NA	S	naked	HA	NA	S	naked	HA	NA	S
SN	8.3E + 10	9.5E + 10	6.1E + 10	1.2E + 11	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %	36 %	47 %	34 %	60 %
L-CC	7.3E + 10	9.2E + 10	5.6E + 10	1.3E + 11	88 %	96 %	93 %	109 %	-	-	-	-

2.9. Infective particle titer determination

Quantification of infective baculovirus titer was performed with tissue culture infective dose 50 (TCID₅₀) on *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Sf9) cells. Sf9 cells in exponential growth phase were diluted to 0.4×10^6 cells/mL. 100 μ L of this dilution were dispensed into each well of a 96-well plate and incubated for 1 h at 27 °C to allow cell attachment. Samples were analyzed in duplicates and 1:10 prediluted with HyClone medium (HyClone SFM4Insect, Cytiva, Uppsala, Sweden). In a 96-well plate, a further 1:5 dilution was performed. Virus sample dilutions were transferred to the 96-well plates with the attached Sf9 cells. A volume of 30 μ L of each virus dilution was added to each well. Plates were incubated at 27 °C for 5 days. After incubation, the plates were inspected with a Leica DM IL LED Inverted Laboratory Fluorescence Microscope (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany). For calculation of the TCID₅₀ value per mL an equation modified from Reed and Muench [31] was used. For conversion to pfu/mL units a poisson distribution-derived factor was utilized.

2.10. Mass spectrometry

Selected samples (LCC, LCH, CH-FT1, CH-FT3, CH-EL2-5) of the gag-HA run were further analyzed via mass spectrometry (MS).

Therefore, the proteins were S-alkylated with iodoacetamide and digested with Trypsin (Promega). The samples were digested in-solution. The digested samples were loaded on a nanoEase C18 column (nanoEase M/Z HSS T3 Column, 100 Å, 1.8 μ m, 300 μ m X 150 mm, Waters) using 0.1 % formic acid as the aqueous solvent. A gradient from 1 % B (B: 80 % Acetonitrile, 0.1 % FA) to 40 % B in 50 min was applied, followed by a 10 min gradient from 40 % B to 95 % B, that facilitates elution of large peptides, at a flow rate of 6 μ L/min. Detection was performed with an Orbitap MS (Exploris 480, Thermo) equipped with the standard H-ESI source in positive ion, DDA mode (=switching to

MSMS mode for eluting peaks). MS-scans were recorded (range: 350–1200 Da) and the 20 highest peaks were selected for fragmentation. Instrument calibration was performed using Pierce FlexMix Calibration Solution (Thermo Scientific).

The analysis files were analyzed using MaxQuant. The files were searched against a *T. ni* database, a baculovirus database, an insect cell EV database [32] (see [Supplementary Material B for databases](#)) and the co-expressed proteins HIV-1 gag (Pr55(Gag)) and Hemagglutinin (strain A/Puerto Rico/8/1934 H1N1). For quantitative comparability, results were normalized to the respective injection volume and the respective particle concentration of each sample. Cluster analysis was performed using the Ward method, and the results were visualized with heatmaps, considering the Top 3 intensities for every protein hit.

3. Results and discussion

The objective of this study was to investigate the applicability of heparin affinity chromatography as a platform process for separation and purification of chimeric enveloped VLPs regardless of the presence of different surface antigens.

Four different VLP constructs based on HIV-1 gag were tested and compared to each other: one HIV-1 gag VLP without additional surface antigens (“gag-naked”), and three HIV-1 gag VLPs carrying either H1 Hemagglutinin (“gag-HA”) or Neuraminidase 2 (“gag-NA”) surface antigens, both from Influenza virus A, or the Spike protein from SARS-CoV-2 (“gag-S”).

3.1. Flow-through chromatography as pre-purification step to remove small impurities

Before the flow-through chromatography, clarified cell culture supernatant (SN) was filtered over a 0.8 μ m membrane in order to remove any potential remaining large impurities such as cell debris. In the

Fig. 1. Exemplary chromatogram for the Capto™ Core 700 pre-purification step of HIV-1 gag naked VLP. The chromatogram shows the online measured UV 280 data (blue solid trace), the 90° light scattering (LS) signal (orange solid trace) and the percentage of buffer B indicating the elution gradient (black dotted trace). Volumes of fractions are indicated on the x-axis: flow-through (FT), wash (W), elution (EL) and CIP. UV 280 and LS 90° were normalized to the respective highest value in the dataset. A normalization value of 1 corresponds to the following maximum values: 4054 mAU (UV 280), 544 mV (LS 90°). 5 % of buffer B corresponds to a conductivity of 12.3 mS/cm and 100 % B to a conductivity of 153.0 mS/cm. Chromatograms of the other VLP constructs can be found in [Supplementary Material A \(Figure S1\)](#). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 3

Fraction volumes, particle concentrations, dsDNA and total protein concentrations of the pre-purification step (Capto™ Core), SN: insect cell culture supernatant after centrifugation, L-CC: 0.8 μm filtered cell culture supernatant, FT-CC: flow-through fraction.

Surface antigen	naked	HA	NA	S	naked	HA	NA	S
Volume [mL]								
	185.0	217.2	237.3	201.1				
NTA	particle concentration (part/mL)				recovery (%)			
Sample								
SN	8.3E + 10	9.5E + 10	6.1E + 10	1.2E + 11	–	–	–	–
L-CC	7.3E + 10	9.2E + 10	5.6E + 10	1.3E + 11	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %
FT-CC	6.1E + 10	5.1E + 10	3.5E + 10	4.0E + 10	83 %	55 %	61 %	32 %
PicoGreen	dsDNA concentration [ng/mL]				recovery (%)			
Sample								
SN	6715.2	5312.2	5531.7	1883.4	–	–	–	–
L-CC	6506.4	5335.6	5699.1	1879.7	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %
FT-CC	504.7	584.3	623.2	141.1	8 %	11 %	11 %	8 %
Bradford	protein concentration [μg/mL]				recovery (%)			
Sample								
SN	404.3	468.2	481.3	246.1	–	–	–	–
L-CC	403.7	455.5	471.4	276.9	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %
FT-CC	53.0	77.1	57.1	52.5	13 %	17 %	12 %	19 %

resulting material (L-CC), a total particle recovery ranging from 88 % to 109 % was observed (Table 2). At this early process stage, total particle concentration measurements by NTA includes not only the product (VLPs), but also other particles, such as baculovirus, EVs, chromatin and cell debris. Lower particle recovery during the filtration step was observed for cell culture supernatants with lower cell viability at harvest (Table 2). In cell cultures with lower cell viability, higher amounts of cell debris are expected in the supernatant. As these are removed by the filtration step, the lower total particle recovery was expected.

The core-shell resin Capto™ Core 700 was used to remove small impurities, such as host cell proteins and DNA. These impurities have the potential to interfere with the subsequent heparin affinity chromatography step, as many proteins have heparin-binding properties or are highly positively charged and capable of binding to the negatively charged heparin [12,14]. 20 CV of filtered cell culture supernatants were loaded on 9.25 – 11.86 mL (Table 1) Capto™ Core 700 columns at a residence time of 5 min. The flow-through fraction (Fig. 1, light scattering signal: LS90°) resulted in a total particle yield between 32 % and 83 % (Table 3). The varying yield between runs can be partially explained by batch-to-batch variations in the production. Besides that, production of different VLP constructs may result in different

productivities for both VLP product and particle impurities. Although the exclusion of VLPs and baculovirus from the beads' active core and their subsequent flow-through is expected due to their large size, other particle impurities, such as extracellular vesicles or chromatin/nucleosomes, might be sufficiently small to enter the active core and be retained, explaining the loss in total particle yield. The baculovirus concentration measured by TCID50 was 0.3 logs lower in the flow-through compared to the load (data not shown). A removal of baculovirus in this step was not expected and the difference can be explained by the intrinsic variability of the assay. Specific Western blots for protein markers associated with VLPs (p24) and baculovirus (vp39) showed that most of these particles passed through the column and were mainly found in the flow-through fraction (Fig. 3A and B). p24 bands in the elution of the pre-purification step can be explained by the presence of soluble protein or protein released by disrupted particles as in this fraction only < 1 % of particles are present (Table S1, Supplementary Material A). H3 histone was used as an indicator for presence of chromatin/nucleosome structures. Respective Western blots showed the removal/reduction of H3 histone protein during the flow-through chromatography (Fig. 3C), supporting the hypothesis that in this step smaller particles were removed.

Fig. 2. SDS-PAGEs of the pre-purification (Capto™ Core) runs: gag-naked (A1); gag-HA (A2); gag-NA (A3); gag-S (A4); The fractions shown are: SN: supernatant; LCC: load; FTCC: flow-through; WCC: wash; ELCC: elution; M: MW marker.

Fig. 3. HIV-1 p24 (A), baculovirus vp39 (B) and histone H3 (C) Western blots for the respective constructs (1: gag-naked, 2: gag-HA, 3: gag-NA, 4: gag-S) showing the fractions of the pre-purification step (Capto™ Core), M: MW marker; SN: supernatant; LCC: Load; FTCC: flow-through; WCC: wash; ELCC: elution fractions.

Fig. 4. Chromatograms of the heparin affinity chromatography step of the investigated HIV-1 gag VLP constructs. The chromatograms show the online measured UV 280 data (blue solid trace), the 90° light scattering (LS) signal (orange solid trace) and the percentage of buffer B indicating the elution gradient (black dotted trace). UV 280 and LS 90° were normalized to the respective highest value in the dataset. A normalization value of 1 corresponds to the following maximum values: gag-naked: 2549 mAU (UV 280), 496 mV (LS 90°); gag-HA: 2604 mAU (UV 280), 580 mV (LS 90°); gag-NA: 2582 mAU (UV 280), 538 mV (LS 90°); gag-S: 2399 mAU (UV 280), 182 mV (LS 90°); 5 % of buffer B corresponds to a conductivity of 12.3 mS/cm and 100 % B to a conductivity of 153.0 mS/cm. Relevant fractions are shown: flow-through (FT1 – FT3), wash (W), elution (E1 – E6). Full chromatograms can be found in Supplementary Material A (Figure S2). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 4

Fraction volumes, particle, dsDNA and TCID50 concentrations of the heparin affinity purification step, SN: insect cell culture supernatant after centrifugation, Load: loading material for the Capto™ Heparin column (=flow-through of Capto™ Core pre-purification step), FT1-3: flow-through fractions, W: wash fraction, EL1-6: elution fractions.

Surface antigen	naked	HA	NA	S	naked	HA	NA	S
Volume [mL]								
Sample								
SN	90.5	108.6	124.7	106.6				
Load	90.5	108.6	124.7	106.6				
FT1	30.2	36.3	41.6	35.6				
FT2	30.2	36.3	41.6	35.6				
FT3	30.1	36.0	41.5	35.4				
W	27.1	32.6	37.4	32.0				
EL1	18.2	21.8	25.0	21.4				
EL2	18.2	21.8	25.0	21.4				
EL3	18.2	21.8	25.0	21.4				
EL4	18.2	21.8	25.0	21.4				
EL5	18.2	21.8	25.0	21.4				
EL6	17.6	21.3	24.6	20.9				
NTA								
particle concentration (part/mL)				recovery of bound particles [%]				
Sample								
SN	8.3E + 10	9.5E + 10	6.1E + 10	1.2E + 11	–	–	–	–
Load	6.1E + 10	5.1E + 10	3.5E + 10	4.0E + 10	–	–	–	–
FT1	1.7E + 10	1.7E + 10	8.4E + 09	1.0E + 10	–	–	–	–
FT2	2.8E + 10	2.4E + 10	1.4E + 10	1.6E + 10	–	–	–	–
FT3	3.7E + 10	2.5E + 10	1.5E + 10	1.9E + 10	–	–	–	–
W	7.1E + 09	3.3E + 09	2.8E + 09	4.5E + 09	–	–	–	–
EL1	<LLQ	6.0E + 08	4.3E + 09	3.8E + 09	0 %	0 %	4 %	3 %
EL2	1.4E + 10	1.8E + 10	1.5E + 10	1.6E + 10	9 %	13 %	14 %	13 %
EL3	2.3E + 10	1.3E + 10	8.1E + 09	1.2E + 10	15 %	10 %	8 %	10 %
EL4	1.3E + 10	1.1E + 10	7.1E + 09	1.8E + 10	8 %	8 %	7 %	15 %
EL5	6.5E + 09	4.9E + 09	4.2E + 09	5.3E + 09	4 %	4 %	4 %	4 %
EL6	3.8E + 09	3.4E + 09	3.0E + 09	1.8E + 09	2 %	2 %	3 %	1 %
PicoGreen								
dsDNA concentration [ng/mL]				recovery [%]				
Sample								
SN	6715.2	5312.2	5531.7	1883.4	–	–	–	–
Load	504.7	584.3	623.2	141.1	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %
FT1	88.4	168.4	130.9	45.1	6 %	10 %	7 %	11 %
FT2	168.0	225.6	224.6	68.4	11 %	13 %	12 %	16 %
FT3	221.8	290.9	299.1	71.2	15 %	17 %	16 %	17 %
W	49.4	67.8	82.6	20.5	3 %	3 %	4 %	4 %
EL1	<LLQ	<LLQ	86.9	59.8	0 %	0 %	3 %	9 %
EL2	104.0	187.8	532.3	123.0	4 %	6 %	17 %	17 %
EL3	968.4	820.4	750.8	179.5	39 %	28 %	24 %	26 %
EL4	558.5	270.0	308.6	136.9	22 %	9 %	10 %	19 %
EL5	459.8	189.9	221.2	85.9	18 %	7 %	7 %	12 %
EL6	258.2	115.4	147.4	59.5	10 %	4 %	5 %	8 %
TCID50								
mean titer [pfu/mL]				recovery [%]				
Sample								
SN	5.6E + 06	4.9E + 06	9.3E + 05	3.3E + 06	–	–	–	–
Load	5.1E + 06	4.0E + 06	2.2E + 06	9.6E + 05	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %
FT1	1.2E + 05	6.0E + 04	1.9E + 04	1.7E + 05	1 %	1 %	0 %	6 %
FT2	3.9E + 05	1.8E + 05	6.2E + 04	2.9E + 05	3 %	2 %	1 %	10 %
FT3	1.0E + 06	8.3E + 05	5.5E + 05	2.6E + 05	6 %	7 %	8 %	9 %
W	5.4E + 05	2.3E + 05	3.9E + 04	1.2E + 05	3 %	2 %	1 %	4 %
EL1	2.2E + 04	2.7E + 04	6.6E + 04	5.4E + 04	0 %	0 %	1 %	1 %
EL2	8.5E + 05	7.9E + 05	2.0E + 05	2.7E + 05	3 %	4 %	2 %	6 %
EL3	1.2E + 06	1.9E + 06	1.6E + 06	1.1E + 06	5 %	10 %	14 %	23 %
EL4	1.2E + 07	5.3E + 06	5.1E + 06	3.3E + 06	46 %	27 %	47 %	68 %
EL5	5.9E + 06	6.7E + 06	1.3E + 06	7.9E + 05	23 %	34 %	12 %	16 %
EL6	2.1E + 06	1.3E + 06	2.6E + 05	5.8E + 04	8 %	6 %	2 %	1 %

The key feature of the core-shell resin is its large capacity to remove small impurities whereas large particles are recovered in the flow-through. While in a size exclusion chromatography a maximum of 0.3 CV could be loaded, using the core-shell resin Capto™ Core 700 allowed for a loading of 20 CV of filtered cell culture supernatant. Pre-purifying the VLPs with this strategy lowered the total protein concentration by 81 – 88 % (Table 3). This depletion was corroborated by SDS-PAGE analysis, in which the flow-through fractions showed less or less intense bands than the loading material (Fig. 2).

(Fig. 3).

dsDNA content was reduced by about one order of magnitude (89 % to 93 % removal, Table 3). This not only ensures that the dsDNA concentration is lowered and possible interaction during the next

purification step is minimized but also suggests that a pre-treatment of the cell-culture supernatant with nucleases is not necessary.

3.2. Separation of HIV-1 gag VLPs and baculovirus particles by heparin affinity chromatography

In this purification step, the potential of heparin to bind to different viral structures was exploited. During the production of enveloped VLPs, cells additionally release other bionanoparticles such as extracellular vesicles along with the replicating baculovirus. These different particles are still present in the pre-purified material together with the VLPs. Therefore, the heparin affinity chromatography step aimed to separate the chimeric HIV-1 gag VLPs displaying different surface antigens from

Fig. 5. HIV-1 p24 (A), baculovirus vp39 (B) and co-expressed surface antigen (C) Western blots of the respective runs (1: gag-naked, 2: gag-HA, 3: gag-NA, 4: gag-S) showing the fractions of the second chromatographic purification step (Capto™ Heparin), M: MW marker; SN: supernatant; L: Load; FT1 - FT3: flow-through 1 – 3; W: wash; EL1 – EL7: elution fractions, Reg: Regeneration.

baculovirus particles, chromatin and other EVs.

10 CV of Capto™ Core 700 flow-through material were loaded onto the column at a residence time of 5 min, followed by a wash step. Elution was performed by a linear salt gradient. During the whole run, the in-line MALS signal was measured and recorded to follow the particle content in real time (Fig. 4). UV signals at 280 and 260 nm were monitored as well (Supplementary Material A, Figure S3).

An immediate breakthrough of particles during loading and two overlapping peaks during elution could be observed for all four different chimeric VLPs (Fig. 4). In order to understand the composition of the particle populations of both breakthrough and elution fractions, particle concentrations were measured by NTA, protein composition by Western blots and SDS-PAGE, concentration of infective baculovirus by TCID50, and dsDNA concentration by PicoGreen assay (Table 4).

Total particle numbers of the loading materials were between 4.3×10^{12} and 5.5×10^{12} particles. An immediate breakthrough, as observed by the MALS signal in the chromatograms, was confirmed by NTA in the three flow-through fractions (Table 4, NTA, FT1 – FT3). Between 38 and 49 % of the loaded particles passed through the column and were collected in the flow-through and wash fractions without being bound. Particles present in the flow-through are extracellular vesicles and other bionanoparticles which do not show any affinity to Heparin, as also confirmed by Mass spectrometry (further discussed in section 3.3). Similar results were observed during the purification of VLPs produced in CHO and HEK 293 cells [12,14]. The rising MALS signal during loading is explained by additional breakthrough of particles such as baculovirus, as demonstrated by the increasing TCID50 from fraction FT1 to FT3 (Table 4). Similarly, it can be expected that some VLPs are also present in the later flow-through fractions. The presence of p24, HA,

NA and S proteins in the flow-through fractions (Western blots, Fig. 5A and C) can indicate the presence of unbound VLPs but also that some of the gag protein and surface antigens are associated with EVs, baculovirus or present as soluble proteins. It is expected that any membrane-associated protein can be found on any particle budding from the same cell membrane. Contrarily, the vp39 protein, the major capsid protein of the baculovirus, is a better indicator for the presence of baculovirus particles as it is not associated to the membrane and therefore not expected to be present on other budded particles.

51 – 62 % of the loaded particles were bound on the column of which 43 – 52 % were recovered during elution (Table 4, NTA). The first peak (fractions EL2 and EL3) eluted at a conductivity of 18 – 25 mS/cm and the second peak (fractions EL4 and EL5) at 45 – 46 mS/cm. Although no baseline separation of the different particle populations could be achieved, the analytical data strongly suggests that HIV-1 gag VLPs were enriched in the first peak (fractions EL2 and EL3) and baculovirus particles in the second peak (fractions EL4 and EL5). In the Western blots, p24 shows strong bands in EL2 and EL3 whereas the signals for vp39 are most prominent in EL4 and EL5 (Fig. 5A and B). This was observed as well in the proteomic analysis, with higher intensities for p24 in EL2 and for vp39 in EL4 and EL5 (Supplementary Material A, Figure S4). p24 is not a specific marker for the VLPs because it can be found on other particles' surfaces released by the host cell such as baculovirus and EVs. Moreover, baseline separation was not achieved during elution and it is expected that some amount of the VLPs is present in the later elution fraction due to peak tailing. This is the reason why p24 is spread out through all fractions with varying intensities. Additionally, the largest portion of infective baculovirus was found in the fractions EL4, EL5 and EL6 (Table 4, TCID50).

Fig. 6. Heatmap of the MS analysis with the baculovirus database screening. For MS analysis, relevant fractions (LCH, FTCH1 and 3, EL2 and EL4) were selected and results were normalized to the injection volume and individual particle concentration of each sample. On the left-hand side, the accession numbers of the proteins are listed, a darker color in the heatmap indicates a higher relative intensity of the respective protein. Further discussed areas on the heatmap are indicated as green, blue and orange boxes. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

In the main product fraction (EL2), 9 % (HIV-1 gag-naked), 13 % (HIV-1 gag-HA), 14 % (HIV-1 gag-NA) and 13 % (HIV-1 gag-S) of bound particles could be recovered. Assuming a hypothetical dose (10^9

particles) the purity of the main product fraction (EL2) was assessed [12]. Accordingly, the dsDNA content per dose was $7.3 \text{ ng}/10^9$ particles (HIV-1 gag-naked), $7.6 \text{ ng}/10^9$ particles (HIV-1 gag-S), $10.5 \text{ ng}/10^9$

Fig. 7. Results of the MS analysis with the insect cell EV database screening. For MS analysis, the most relevant fractions (LCH, FTCH1 and 3, EL2 and EL4) were selected and results were normalized to the injection volume and individual particle concentration of each sample. On the left-hand side, the accession numbers of the proteins are listed, a darker color in the heatmap indicates a higher relative intensity of the respective protein. The further discussed area on the heatmap is indicated as a green box. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

particles (HIV-1 gag-HA) and 35.9 ng/10⁹ particles (HIV-1 gag-NA). The guidelines for vaccine manufacturing recommend < 10 ng residual dsDNA per dose. With our purification platform we obtained products which are close to the specifications. The higher dsDNA content per dose in the gag-NA VLP can be explained by the low titer. In this case the separation power was not sufficient to meet the specifications and an endonuclease treatment could be considered [33]. Additionally, host cell protein content was below the limit of quantification (data not shown) and in the main product fraction an average seven-fold reduction of baculovirus could be obtained (Supplementary Material A, Table S2).

3.3. Proteomic analysis

To further evaluate the separation performance, samples from the gag-HA run were analyzed by mass spectrometry with respect to baculovirus and EV marker proteins and protein heatmaps were created.

The first heatmap confirms that baculovirus was enriched in the second peak of the heparin affinity chromatography step (Fig. 6, EL4). During loading on Capto™ Heparin, the observed baculovirus breakthrough in the later fraction (Fig. 6, FT3) is also confirmed.

As previously discussed, due to the similar budding process of different bionanoparticles, many membrane proteins (glycoproteins and envelope-associated proteins) of a specific bionanoparticle will be present on other particles budding from the same cell membrane. Accordingly, glycoproteins and other envelope-associated proteins from the baculovirus proteome can also be present on the surfaces of other particles, such as VLPs or EVs, and were therefore identified in the different fractions containing different particle populations. On the other hand, capsid-associated and other non-membrane-associated proteins are less likely to be found in other bionanoparticles and are consequently more reliable for identifying baculovirus. This can be observed on the heatmap (Fig. 6) where for many proteins the bands are more intense in EL4: e.g. for an uncharacterized 38.0 kDa protein (Accession number P24745.2, green box) and *Protein AC 54* (P41458.1, blue box), which both have been found to be capsid-associated [34,35], or *Capsid-associated protein VP80* (Q00733.1, orange box); as well as for proteins which are non-membrane-associated but involved into the internal viral life cycle like *DNA replication helicase* (P24307.2), *Alkaline nuclease* (P24731.1, both in green box) and *Putative superoxide dismutase [Cu-Zn]* (P24705.1, blue box) or *Protein Ac66* (P41467.1, orange box) which is crucial for the efficient egress of nucleocapsids from the nucleus and general synthesis of virions [36]. The concurrent presence of many of those proteins in FT3 can be explained by the breakthrough of baculovirus particles at this point.

Proteomic data was also compared against a database of possible insect cell EV markers determined in the work of Hausjell et al. [32]. MS analysis confirmed that many of those markers can exclusively or in higher intensity be found in the flow-through fractions of the Capto™ Heparin (Fig. 7), as also observed in the purification of HIV-1 gag VLPs produced in HEK 293 cells [12]. For instance, some of the markers being absent in EL2 (green box) are membrane proteins like tetraspanins (Accession numbers A0A7E5WP87 and A0A7E5VQB9), integrin (A0A7E5WQ73) or syntenin-1-like (A0A7E5WQ52), all of them being EV-associated. These findings support the hypothesis that also for HIV-1 gag VLPs produced in insect cell culture, separation of VLPs and EVs can be achieved via heparin affinity chromatography. Interestingly, when using a different buffer system with a lower ionic strength, heparin affinity chromatography can also be used for the capture and purification of EVs as shown by Barnes et al. [37].

4. Conclusion

The current study demonstrates that a two-step chromatographic process, in which core-shell flow-through and heparin affinity chromatography are combined, functions independently of surface antigens

displayed on HIV-1 gag VLPs. This method has been previously used to purify naked gag VLPs. Here we demonstrate the platformability of this process for chimeric HIV-1 gag VLPs displaying hemagglutinin or neuraminidase from influenza A virus or the spike protein from SARS-CoV-2, and the VLP without co-expressed surface protein. The use of core-shell technology is proven to be an effective tool in preparing VLP material for heparin affinity chromatography by removing small impurities such as HCPs and free dsDNA. A further advantage is that the flow-through of the first chromatography step can be directly loaded into the second one without further conditioning. A successful separation of VLPs, EVs and baculovirus particles through heparin affinity chromatography was demonstrated by Western blots, proteomic analysis and TCID50 with a seven-fold reduction of baculovirus in the main product fraction. The purity of the main product fraction was assessed assuming a hypothetical dose of 10⁹ particles. Remaining dsDNA content varied between 7 and 36 ng/dose and the total protein content was under the limit of quantification, meeting requirements for a viral vaccine. A yield of 9 – 14 % of bound particles with a concentration between 1.4 and 1.8 × 10¹⁰ particles/mL was achieved in the main product fraction. Conclusively, this process is suitable as a platform for purification of chimeric HIV-1 gag-based VLP products.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alexander M. Zollner: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Leticia Guzman Ruiz:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Viktoria Mayer:** Methodology, Conceptualization. **Stefanie Stohl:** Investigation. **Leo A. Jakob:** Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nico Lingg:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Miriam Klausberger:** Supervision, Conceptualization. **Alois Jungbauer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Patricia Pereira Aguilar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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